

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF SUPPORTING AND DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INDIVIDUAL ABILITIES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the psychological, pedagogical and social aspects of the development of individual characteristics of students in higher education institutions. The article discusses psychological aspects in the formation and development of students' personalities, including motivation, emotional intelligence, stress management and personal identification processes. As for pedagogical aspects, it is shown that through an individual approach, person-centered education and interactive methods, students can realize their potential to the highest level. Social aspects affect the development of students through social responsibility, friendship, cooperation and interaction. The article emphasizes the need to create the necessary pedagogical conditions for students to achieve academic and personal success by improving their psychological and social skills. This approach will serve not only to increase the effectiveness of students in the learning process, but also to be successful in their future professional activities.

Key words: student, individual characteristics, psychological development, pedagogical approach, social skills, motivation, emotional intelligence, interactive learning.

In the higher education system, the development of students' individual characteristics is considered one of the main goals of education. Each student has his own psychological, pedagogical and social characteristics, which directly affect their success and personal development in the educational process.

The development of students' individual characteristics helps not only to increase their academic achievements, but also to strengthen their social and emotional skills. This article analyzes the psychological, pedagogical and social aspects of the development of students' individual characteristics. Psychological aspects play an important role in the development of students' individual characteristics. Psychology studies various aspects of personal development, which directly affect the effectiveness of the educational process. Psychological aspects include the following important areas of student development: 1. Personal identification and self-awareness. One of the main aspects of psychological development is the process of a student's understanding of his own identity [1]. The student tries to understand himself by setting his goals, assessing his personal abilities and understanding his social role. In the process of personal identification, students determine how they want to see themselves in society and how to form their knowledge and skills. These changes increase the student's internal motivation in the educational process and lead to openness to change [2]. 2. Motivation and intellectual abilities. Motivation is of great importance in the development of individual characteristics of students. Motivation encourages students to achieve their goals. From a psychological point of view, motivation is divided into two main types: internal motivation (the desire to develop oneself) and external motivation (getting good grades, increasing one's reputation in society). The development of personal needs and intellectual abilities is the main tool for students to achieve success in their studies. At the same time, motivation supports development not only in academic, but also in personal and social aspects of study. 3. Emotional intelligence [3]. Emotional intelligence is the

ability to manage, understand, and effectively communicate with others. The development of emotional intelligence helps a student understand himself, manage his emotions, and overcome stress. During the educational process, students often experience stress and anxiety, so the development of their emotional intelligence is very important. By understanding and managing their emotions, a student increases his ability to effectively respond to various situations in his studies and life[5]. 4. Stress and adaptation. In higher education institutions, students often try to adapt to a new environment and the difficulties of the educational process. Psychological support and stress management methods are very important for students, they help ensure effective learning. With the help of stress management and adaptation methods, a student effectively enters the educational process and achieves success in assimilating new information [6].

Pedagogical aspects. Pedagogical aspects play a special role in the development of individual characteristics of students. The pedagogical approach is aimed at developing the personality of students, and the content and methods of the educational process are adapted to individual needs. Pedagogical aspects consist of the following elements: 1. Individual approach. Each student is unique, his abilities and needs are different. It is important to take into account individual characteristics in the pedagogical approach [7]. In order for students to feel comfortable, the teacher must analyze the abilities, needs and motivation of each student. With the help of this approach, educational methods and styles are selected that are appropriate for the development of the student. Through an individual approach, the teacher helps students find their place. 2. Person-centered education. Person-centered education is an educational process based on the needs, interests and capabilities of the student. From a pedagogical point of view, this approach helps the student to understand himself and discover his potential. Students feel understood and supported by the teacher, which increases their self-confidence. At the same time, the teacher helps the student to express himself and be open to change. 3. Interactive and communicative methods. Interactive pedagogical methods are important in developing the individual characteristics of students. These methods encourage students to actively participate in the learning process, and also allow them to freely express their thoughts. Group work, discussions, role-playing games and other interactive methods develop students' communication skills. With the help of these methods, the student learns to express his thoughts openly and clearly. 4. Experiments and practices. Along with theoretical knowledge, practical experiences are also important for students in the process of higher education. Experiments and practices create an opportunity for students to test themselves in a real environment. In this process, students test their abilities and acquire new knowledge. Practical training allows students to identify and develop their potential.

Social aspects. Social aspects play an important role in the development of students' individual characteristics, because in the educational environment, students interact with each other and learn how to see themselves in society. The influence of social relations and the environment is of great importance in the development of students. 1. Support of the educational environment. The support of the social and pedagogical environment for students in higher education institutions helps to develop their individual characteristics. A supportive environment gives students confidence in changing themselves, developing their potential and mastering new knowledge. In this environment, students have a strong motivation that encourages them to achieve their social and academic goals. 2. Social relations between students. Social relations, friendship and cooperation between students make the process of mutual learning and development more effective. Students develop their social skills by exchanging ideas, solving problems and supporting each other. Social connections also form students' sense of empathy, sympathy and social responsibility [8]. 3. Social responsibility and ethics. Students should understand their social responsibility and realize their ethical and moral

obligations to society. Social responsibility helps students fulfill their duties, ensure justice and equality, and benefit society.

Social responsibility is of great importance in the development of individual characteristics. Students should understand their social duties, realize their responsibility to society. This, in turn, teaches students to respect moral standards, justice and equality. A student who understands his social responsibility will not only achieve success in the educational process, but will also have the opportunity to actively participate in the team and contribute to the development of society.

The development of individual characteristics of students has a significant impact not only on their academic success, but also on their personal and social development. This process helps to form a sense of mutual respect, cooperation and responsibility among students, as well as develop the skills necessary for future professional activities. Therefore, pedagogical approaches and strategies aimed at developing individual characteristics of students increase the effectiveness of the teaching process and ensure the future success of students.

The development of individual characteristics of students is a complex process that includes psychological, pedagogical and social aspects. Psychological aspects, in addition to helping students develop their personal identification and motivation, also serve to increase emotional intelligence. Pedagogical aspects, on the other hand, provide students with the opportunity to improve their abilities through an individual approach and person-centered education. Social aspects ensure the social development of the student through relationships between students in the educational environment and understanding of their place in society. Thus, it is necessary to take into account all aspects in order to create an effective educational system for developing individual characteristics of students.

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